

A Study on the changes in Standard of Living among the Slum Resettlers in Perumbakkam, Chennai

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Abstract:- The slum re settlers are those who resettled from the banks of river to the resettlement colony at perumbakkam because of development induced displacement resettlement. There will be a lot changes in their livelihood capitals when compared to the host place before resettlement. Also the standard of living determines their quality of life in the resettlement colony and the adapting livelihood strategies that they practice to improve or maintain their livelihood and also the new challenges additionally the external factors also affects their livelihood immensely.

In this context, the researchers aims to study the standard of living of the people after the resettlement. The researcher has used mixed method research approach with sequential explanatory design and used interview schedule to collect data from eighty respondents for quantitative and focus group discussion guide & Key informant guide for Qualitative.

The main findings include that after resettlement the standard of living has been decreased due to the less adapting livelihood strategy by the slum resettlers and the livelihood assets has been diminished. This also conclude that because of less adapting livelihood strategies the respondents were only able to maintain the livelihood despite the practice of livelihood diversification and no raise in the standard of living when compared to the data of before resettlement.

The suggestion would be to the government to focus on the human capital of the livelihood to enhance the knowledge and skill of the slum resettlers to adapt to the condition in the positive way to raise their standard of living. The enhancement of human capital is the base to improve in other livelihood capitals.

Keywords:- *adapting strategies, livelihood capitals, livelihood diversification, standard of living.*

I. INTRODUCTION

During the last decades, the rapid growth of urbanization is very high and this urbanization urge to some of the changes in the urban areas and rural too. This type of changes like constructions of buildings, infrastructure facilities, bridges for transportation, dams and beautification and development projects. This developmental projects are useful for the people to access and to make use of it for modernized lifestyle in the city. Even it resembles the development of the city but it ultimately targets the people those are residing near the river and other lands as a group called slum. Most of the development projects targets the people those who are in slum areas and it is not in the case of

the rich people those who are residing on the same site. The resettlement project is almost the failure project as it is not concentrate the livelihood of slum people after the resettlement project rather it provides only the housing that too are not well structured and isolate people from main stream population.

A. *Related Theories*

a) Scudder-Colson Relocation Theory

Scudder and Colson (1982) argued that, relocation, whether voluntary or compulsory, is a stressful experience. Members of community undergoing relocation react in predictable and broadly similar ways, "partially because the stress of relocation limits the range of coping response of those involved". The problems and stress accompanying forced relocation also characterize other types of relocation although to a lesser degree. During the most stressful period i.e. the period leading up to relocation, the move itself, and the first few years of adjustment thereafter, people tend to behave in conservative, risk avoiding ways, clinging to familiar practices and groups. As and if, communities re-establish themselves economically and socially they leave this period of stress and insecurity. People now are to behave in more innovative and risk taking ways, and their attitudes become increasingly flexible, individualistic and open ended - more so than in the case of communities that have not been resettled. This is because the simplified cultural repertoire and the breakdown of patterns of community organization and leadership that occur during resettlement wake for less restraints and individual initiative as the relocated community establish itself A community may be deemed to have successfully passed through relocation experience, when it passed through relocation experience, when it is no longer outside management and when it has become integrated into wider regional setting in such a way that it has attained economic and administrative ability.

b) Michael M. Cernea's Impoverishment Risk Theory

Cernea (1995a, 1997 and 1999) proposed a "Risk Model" consisting of eight convergent sub processes which result in lasting impoverishment, if the risks are not addressed from the outset through the very planning of the development programme that causes displacement. This model shows how impoverishment can occur as a result of displacement. He pointed out that when displacement and relocation leave people worse off, the empirical evidence reveals a set of eight recurrent characteristics. While each is irreducible to others, they have a common denominator: they

contribute to a process of impoverishment. These characteristics make up a risk model. The model points to the "risks to be avoided" in displacement. These major risks reflect social and economic processes that occur with higher No. of Respondents, that others, despite the enormous variability of individuals situations. These are: (a) Landlessness; (b) Joblessness; (c) Homelessness; (d) Marginalization; (e) Morbidity and mortality (f) Food insecurity; (g) Loss of access to common property assets; and (h) Social disarticulation.

B. Related Articles

- a) Impact of Resettlement on the Livelihood of Slum Dwellers: A Case Study on Mandartola Housing Gopalganj Bangladesh

The concluding finding of such relocation process is that it affected the symbiotic relationship of housing and livelihood opportunity. Therefore, this paper suggests that policy makers, planners, public officials, private officials and researchers should pay attention to the improvement of human, social, financial and natural capital rather than only focusing on physical capital during the process of resettlement.

- b) Increasing the Deprivation of the Poor and Impeding the Resilience of the City

This Research article suggest that displacement due to the development is like a cosmetic surgery which concentrate only on the beautification of the city not on the livelihood of slum dwellers which leads to difficulties and leads to impoverishment and separating the people from the mainstream population is considered to be the end of the project resettlement but how it impacts the livelihood of the people is not considered which resembles the impediment to the growth of resilient cities.

- c) Urban Slum Resettlement Program: The Case Of Fushun City

This research article suggests that the resettlement weakens the close neighbourhood relations of original communities. This project has though given the infrastructure facilities and livelihood it failed to improve the social capital and totally the people got disconnected in societal relationship with each other. This urges the people to face insecurities and leads to serious adversities. Also the sustainability was lacking in the given facilities and long term sustainable improvements too. The sustainable development of resettlements is still facing challenges from the single function of redeveloped areas, aging facilities and resident's succession.

- d) The Impact of Slum Resettlement on Urban Integration in Mumbai: The Case of the Chandivali Project

This Research article suggests that changes in livelihood opportunity and pattern leads to unemployment and unavailability of chances in family income growth this leads to disintegration of socio economic status. Employment is the key factor to

drive towards the integration of socio economic status. Social inequality (unequal distribution of income of different groups in the society) and structural changes in family leads nuclearization in the family.

- e) Slum relocation projects in Bangkok (Ranjith Perera 2004)

This Article suggest that the resettlement needs some pre requisites in the community before the implementation of the project. These include factors external to the community such as the location of the new settlement and award of compensation and factors internal to the community such as unity, availability of strong leadership, active participation and positive attitude of community members. The study finds that slum relocation projects require specialized activities in the consolidation stage, in order to sustain the momentum generated at the eviction and transition stage of the projects. This pre requisites is the significant factor to mitigate the new challenges that they are going to face.

- f) Involuntary resettlement, Impoverishment Risks and Sustainable Livelihoods (Dr. Christopher mcdowell)

This Research article suggest that sustainable livelihoods research is primarily not concerned with why people become poor, but rather why poor people remain poor, this article has suggested that insights from SL research are valuable for post-disaster research because they focus attention on the potential to define and measure both the quality and quantity of livelihoods in a given context thereby enabling researchers to understand the impacts of identified risks on livelihoods understanding how people adapt positively and negatively to new situations in order stimulate policy and operational-relevant research to guide targeted interventions the importance attached to understanding institutional processes in resettlers' adaptation strategies will advance our knowledge about the ways in which forced displacement dismantles patterns of social organisation and how they are re-formed to confront new challenges and lastly, the focus on sustainable outcomes of livelihood strategies introduces a more encompassing environmental dimension to research, and adds timeframes to the reconstruction process.

- g) Slum clearance (E.G Goetz, 2012)

This Research article suggests that resettlement urges a change in livelihood pattern and exacerbates the psychological, social, and material deprivations of people living in poverty, disrupting social networks, survival strategies, and access to medical care, food, water, and sanitation.

- h) People's livelihood adaptation in resettlement projects in Laos (Furo-cho, Chikusa-ku Nagoya University, Japan)

This Research Journal paper suggested the adapting strategies of livelihood and how the resettled people in the rural area adapted the situation and how they used

the different livelihood strategy on the different livelihood capitals.

C. Statement of the Problem

Resettlement of slum has become an issue of concern in developing countries. Resettlement poses several risk to vulnerable urban development. Resettlement changes the behaviour and routine works which results in downward on social indicators like education, employment and health of social system and causes effective impact on their livelihood. Resettlement is associated with economic hardship, disruption social fabric, and feeling of uprootment, alienation and psychological trauma. Resettlement in the slum would cause a rise in crime and unemployment.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. General Objective

To study the changes in standard of living among slum resettlers in perumbakkam

B. Specific Objectives

To study the changes in Livelihood opportunity and pattern

To analyze the vulnerability context

To determine their living conditions by analyzing livelihood capitals

To study how are they positively and negatively adapting the situation

To study how are they confronting new challenges
Suggestion on Transforming structure & processes

C. Research Methodology

Mixed method will be used which is characterized by the combination of Quantitative and Qualitative methods. Quantitative method focuses on gathering numerical data and generalizing to explain the particular phenomena. Qualitative method focuses to fully describe and comprehend the subjective meanings of events to individuals and groups.

D. Research Design

The research design is Sequential Explanatory Design. The study uses the Explanatory Design (also known as the Explanatory Sequential Design) is a two-phase mixed methods design. This design starts with the collection and analysis of quantitative data. This first phase is followed by the subsequent collection and analysis of qualitative data. The second, qualitative phase of the study is designed so that it follows from (or connects to) the results of the first quantitative phase. Because this design begins quantitatively, investigators typically place greater emphasis on the quantitative methods than the qualitative methods. They started with a quantitative survey study and identified statistically significant differences and anomalous results.

E. Field Of Study

The field of study is the place where the research is carried out. The field of study is at perumbakkam. Perumbakkam is a suburb of the southern Indian city of Chennai in Chengalpattu district. It is the place where the slum dwellers resettled to the perumbakkam colony from diverse group of slum dwellers who were resided at the banks of coovam river.

F. Universe

Universe is a set of experimental units from which sample are drawn. It is the total of the item in any field of inquiry. The universe of the study is the slum Resettlers in Perumbakkam.

G. Sample Size

Sample size refers to the number of participants included in the study. It measures the number of individual samples included in the study. The researcher has taken 80 respondents for quantitative and 9 and 13 respondents taken for two FGD and 3 respondents for key informant interview for qualitative method.

H. Sampling Technique

Sampling is a technique that allows researchers to obtain knowledge about a population from the findings of a subset of that population. There are number of sampling process. The researcher has used simple random sampling by using lottery method. This sampling comes under probability sampling.

I. Tools

a) Quantitative:

The researcher developed a Google form consisting of questions related to livelihood patterns, vulnerability context, and livelihood capitals.

b) Qualitative:

The researcher has conducted the focus group discussion on adapting strategies and new challenges of slum resettlers.

J. Inclusive Criteria

The respondents should be married and as a family.

The respondents should be the displaced slum dwellers in the perumbakkam resettlement colony.

K. Conceptual Definitions

a) Slum resettlement:

Resettlement in this study refers to the process that takes people to the state of impoverishment and risk factors that diminish the livelihood of the resettled people (Michael. M. cernea 1990)

b) Standard of living

Standard of living focuses on basic material factors such as income, gross domestic product (GDP), life expectancy, and economic opportunity. It is closely related to quality of life, which can also explore factors such as economic and political stability, political and religious freedom, environmental quality, climate, and safety (Investopedia).

L. Operational definition

a) Slum resettlement:

Resettlement is the process of identification and transfer of a group, large or small, from their local habitat/ native place to a host place, from the main stream population (local habitat/ native place-comfortable zone) to a host place, an unfavorable environment (discomfort zone).

b) Standard of living

Standard of living defines the positive and negative impact on the livelihood outcome which shows the wellbeing aspects of the person in the society.

M. Data Analysis

The data collected will be analysed using SPSS (Statistical package for social sciences) quantitative analysis and Open coding and axial coding for qualitative analysis

III. RESULTS

A. Changes in Livelihood pattern

a) Food Insecurity

The Table I shows that more than two third 65% of the respondents said they face food insecurity and more than one third 35% of the respondents said that they didn't face any food insecurity.

Food Insecurity	No. of Respondents	Percent
Yes	52	65.0
No	28	35.0
Total	80	100.0

Table 1: Food Insecurity

b) Unemployment Rate

The Table II shows the employment status after resettlement one third (31.2%) of the respondents were employed after resettlement and more than two third (68.8%) of the respondents were unemployed after resettlement

Employment status after resettlement	No. of Respondents	Percent
Employed	25	31.2
Unemployed	55	68.8
Total	80	100.0

Table 2: Unemployment Rate

c) Educational Status of Children

The Table III shows the educational status of children after resettlement a considerable population (12.5%) of the respondents were pursuing education and less than one fourth (23.8%) of the respondents were completed the education and more than one third (63.8%) of the respondents were drop out.

Educational status of children after resettlement	No. of Respondents	Percent
Pursuing	10	12.5
Completed	19	23.8
Drop out	51	63.8
Total	80	100.0

Table 3: Educational Status Of Children

d) Morbidity

The Table IV shows that that less than half 45% of the respondents said mixture of drainage water and half of the respondents 55% said appearance of black colour.

Kind of water supplied	No. of Respondents	Percent
Mixture of drainage water	36	45.0
Appearance of black colour	44	55.0
Total	80	100.0

Table 4: Kind Of Water Supplied

B. Vulnerability Context

a) Trends

The Fig. 1. shows the vulnerability context of the community people in the resettlement colony because of economic trends less than one fourth (21%) of the respondents said that always it affects the livelihood of the people and vast majority (79%) of the respondents said that it often affects their livelihood. the vulnerability context of the community people in the resettlement colony because of technological trends less than one fourth (70%) of the respondents said that sometimes it affects the livelihood of the people and more than one fourth (30%) of the respondents said that it rarely affects their livelihood. The vulnerability context of the community people in the resettlement colony because of political trends, a considerable population (20%) of the respondents said that sometimes it affects the livelihood of the people and a vast majority (80%) of the respondents said that it rarely affects their livelihood.

Fig. 1. Trends

b) Shocks

The Fig. 2. shows the vulnerability context of the community people in the resettlement colony because of natural disaster (shocks), half (57%) of the respondents said that often it affects the livelihood of the people and a vast majority (43%) of the respondents said that it sometimes affects their livelihood. The vulnerability context because of diseases & death (shocks), less than half (40%) of the respondents said that often it affects the livelihood of the people and more than two third (60%) of the respondents said that it sometimes affects their livelihood.

Fig. 2: Shocks

c) Seasonality

The Fig. 3. shows the vulnerability context of the community people in the resettlement colony because of prices (seasonality), all the respondents said that often it affects the livelihood of the people. The vulnerability context because of employment opportunities (seasonality), less than half (42.5%) of the respondents said that often it affects the livelihood of the people and half (57.5%) of the respondents said that it sometimes affects their livelihood.

Fig. 3: Seasonality

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Changes in Livelihood pattern

From this overall findings of changes in livelihood pattern of slum resettlers at perumbakkam is that 100% of the respondents have often morbidity because of often supply of contaminated water, also more than two third 65% of the respondents face food insecurity and after resettlement unemployment rate has been increased because of resettlement, people separated from main stream population and leads to the emerging factors as low socio-economic background and loss of identity, Also the education pattern of the children changed after resettlement data shows that more than two third 63% of the respondents said that their children are drop out. These findings are related to the theory of Michael M. Cernea (Impoverishment Risk & Reconstruction model) which defines the joblessness, food insecurity, marginalization and morbidity related to this research. Also this research states that changes in the livelihood pattern affects employment and the availability of chances in economic growth which relates to the research book the impact of resettlement on urban integration in Mumbai The case of Chandavali project. Also the changes in livelihood pattern exacerbates the material deprivation of the people in poverty and also access to medical care, food, water and sanitation related to the journal of E.G Goetz 2012 (Slum clearance).

B. Vulnerability Context

In this research vulnerability context is assessed from the model sustainable livelihood framework which defines that vulnerability context is the external factors which affects the livelihood the people like trends, shocks and seasonality. In trends economic trends affects vast majority 79% of the respondents often, technological and political trends affects more than two third 70% of the respondents and a considerable population 20% of the respondents sometimes. Shocks like natural disaster affects half 57% of the respondents and diseases affects less than half 40% of the respondents sometimes. In seasonality, prices factors affects vast majority 80% of the respondents often and employment opportunities affects less than half 43% of the respondents often. This findings shows that despite the resettlement external factors also affects the livelihood of slum resettlers which causes additional stress and adversities.

C. Livelihood capitals

In livelihood capitals all the capitals like Human, physical, natural, financial and social capitals are assessed before and after resettlement to find out the quality of life of the slum resettlers. The Fig. 5. shows that the livelihood capitals after resettlement has a decreased rate when compared with before resettlement (Fig. 4.) This shows that the quality of life lived by the slum resettlers has decreased in all the livelihood assets. (Impact of resettlement on livelihood at mandartola housing Bangladesh, md Ashiq Ur Rahman)

Fig. 4: Livelihood Capitals Before Resettlement

Fig. 5: Livelihood Capitals After Resettlement

D. Adapting Livelihood strategies

In this research the adapting livelihood strategies defines the livelihood diversification which means the urban people construct different portfolio of activities to enhance or maintain their livelihood. Adapting livelihood strategies has divided into three categories according to Dorward it has hanging in, stepping up and stepping out. In hanging in strategy people maintain their livelihood through various activities, in stepping up people used to improve their livelihood and in stepping out people invest from their accumulated assets and improve their standard of living. From the finding all the respondents said that even though they perform various activities their livelihood enhancement was minimum it just help them to maintain their livelihood rather than improving. The concluding finding shows that

even though livelihood diversification was practiced the locality doesn't support the people to improve because perumbakkam is considered to be the area surrounded by technological resources if the locality considered to be the people based resources then livelihood diversification can be possible in improving their livelihood.

E. Confronting New Challenges

The slum resettlers has been facing new challenges like impact of covid-19 which leads to disrupt in education system of the children this online education made disinterest in studies among students. Also usage of more technology and changes in seasonality prices also affects their livelihood and also psychological stress has been raised among slum resettlers. Also weak socialization has been emerged due to covid. From this findings new challenges makes them so weak in their resilience.

F. Transforming structure & process

In this transforming structure & processes related to the sustainable livelihood framework it defines the transformation of government level structure and policies & laws. In this research it developed a model on the basis of increasing the human capitals which leads to development of all the capitals for sustainable livelihood of slum resettlers. The model was developed by the role of bridging in the social work. The researcher was acting as a bridge between the slum resettlers and the Tamil Nadu urban habitat development board to solve and identify the things to be augment.

V. PROPOSED MODEL

The results of the research identified that the perspective of the people's (Slum Resettlers) expectations and the TamilNadu) expectations to be tangible, but there are some interventions to be processed to achieve the complete form of development in the community. This 'Human Capital Model' (Fig. 6.) is proposed as a bridging tool which fosters the development in the community.

Fig. 6: Human Capital Model

VI. CONCLUSION

This study through its detailed examination of resettlement impact in the living standard of people demonstrated that people living in the resettlement colony has long term impacts and declined socio-economic conditions of people leads to the diminished of livelihood capitals like Human, physical, social, natural and financial assets. Also the vulnerability context of the people affects the people more apart from the internal factors. People's adapting nature also decreases due to the constant adversities due to the resettlement and also because of new challenges in covid and consequences raised because of community's indiscipline. This separation of people from the main stream population has deteriorated the lifestyle, livelihood capitals and adapting nature of the people which leads to impoverishment.

Government should be for the welfare of the people in promoting the community into development and not to the state of impoverishment. Therefore, it is concluded that in this research, standard of living of the people in the resettlement colony still make them to be in the state of impoverishment because of no sustainable development from both people and the government.

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